

CONDENSATION OF KETONIC CARBONYL COMPOUNDS WITH CYANOACETIC ESTER IN PRESENCE OF PIPERAZINE DIACETATE

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Piperazine diacetate is found to be effective and useful catalyst in the condensation of carbonyl compounds with ethyl cyanoacetate (Knoevenagel's reaction) since it can be recovered and purified after removal of the products of reaction. Examples of its application are given and new compounds formed in certain cases have been characterised and described.

Since ammonium and amine salts of organic acids are better catalysts than the free bases themselves, Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2327; 1941, 63, 3452) introduced ammonium acetate in presence of acetic acid and many other catalysts as condensing agents in the Knoevenagel reactions. Knoevenagel himself used many salt catalysts in the reaction known after his name (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1905, 11, 76, 179, 726, 1071). The superior catalytic activity of salts in place of either the free acid or the free base in aldol-type reactions finds a ready explanation in Brönsted's extended theory of acidic and basic catalysis (Brönsted, *Chem. Rev.*, 1928, 89, 2327). Ammonium acetate in presence of acetic acid found extensive application in the synthesis of alkylidene-cyanoacetic esters, but a great disadvantage of this catalyst lies in the formation of by-products (Cope *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452; Mukherji, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 91; Cragoe *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 381; Banerjee and Das Gupta, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1318).

Bezzi and Cocco (*Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 44, 5826^c) used piperazine as one of the catalysts in the Knoevenagel condensations and reported high yields. The present author, however, failed to obtain good yields with carbonyl compounds other than those used by the above mentioned workers. The views of Brönsted (*loc. cit.*) and of Cope (*loc. cit.*) led the author to use piperazine diacetate in presence of acetic acid as a better catalyst in such reactions. Actually good yields were obtained in all cases. The new catalyst has the advantage that it does not form any by-product; further, it can be recovered from the aqueous solution after removal of the products of reaction and may be used again after crystallisation from water and subsequent drying.

Based upon the views of Hahn and Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 46) and of Hohler and Casson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1975), Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2329) formulated a mechanism for the Knoevenagel reactions catalysed by the salts which involved the generation of a carbanion from the compound containing reactive methylene group, followed by its addition to the carbonyl component and the subsequent elimination of a molecule of water from the transitory hydroxy compound formed by the addition of a proton to the negatively charged oxygen. The same mechanism should hold good in the reactions catalysed by piperazine diacetate.

Though the new catalyst succeeded in bringing about condensations involving cyanoacetic esters as much as and even better than ammonium acetate, it failed in con-

densing malonic esters with ketones and cyanoacetic esters with hindered ketones like camphor.

As described by Cope (*ibid.*, 1941, 63, 3452) the reactions were carried out in flasks

FIG. 1

attached to a constant water separator (Dean and Stark, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1920, 12, 486). The water-separator (Fig. 1) used by the author has the reaction vessel attached to the st. joint (A) [No. 3 or B. 24]. The azeotropic system of benzene, acetic acid and water passes along (H), condenses in the condenser attached to the st. joint (C), falls along the thin and long funnel (F) in (E), a separatory funnel attached by st. joint at (D). The lower layer of water is taken out through the stop-cock (I). The upper layer of benzene flows back along (G) into the reaction flask at (A). (B) is a 25 ml. dropping funnel which is used to drop a liquid during the reaction. A solid reaction component may be added by detaching (B) from (J), a B-10 joint.

This apparatus may be used for liquid-liquid extraction purposes with the funnel (F) reaching the bottom of the liquid-containing flask attached to (D). (A) carries the flask with the solvent, lighter than water. Other arrangements remain the same.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Ethyl β -Acetopropionate and Ethyl Cyanoacetate in the presence of Piperazine.—To a mixture of ethyl β -acetopropionate (43 g., 0.3 M) and ethyl cyanoacetate (35 g., 0.3M) in benzene (100 ml.) was added piperazine (1.5 g., 0.018M) and refluxed over a short free flame till the separation of water was complete (3 hours). The cooled, dark red solution was washed thrice with water, the solvent removed and the residual oil distilled under vacuum. The yield of the colorless liquid product was 27 g. (35% of theoretical); b.p. 160°/5.5 mm. (cf. Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 423, b.p. 154°-160°/5.5 mm.).

Condensation of Ethyl β -Acetoglutarate and Ethyl Cyanoacetate ; Piperazine Diacetate.—A mixture of ethyl β -acetoglutarate (10.3 g., 0.045M), ethyl cyanoacetate (5.6 g., 0.05M), piperazine (2.15 g., 0.025M), acetic acid (9 ml., 0.15M) and toluene

(80 ml.) was refluxed. Within an hour the separation of water was complete. Solid needles which sublimed during reflux on the upper cooler parts of the reaction vessel had m.p. 225-27° and mixed m.p. 228-30° with piperazine diacetate (m.p. 234°; Birköfer, *Ber.*, 1932, 76B, 429). The cold solution was washed thoroughly with water, the solvent removed and distillation under vacuum yielded 8.5 g. (60% of theoretical) of a liquid, b.p. 125°-126°/1 mm. (Found: C, 58.85; H, 7.33; N, 4.41. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{23}O_6N$ C, 59.07; H, 7.07; N, 4.30 per cent).

The aqueous extract on evaporation gave piperazine diacetate, m.p. 230-31°.

Condensation of Ethyl β -Acetopropionate and Ethyl Cyanoacetate.—To a mixture of ethyl β -acetopropionate (30 g., 0.2M), ethyl cyanoacetate (30 g., 0.25M) and piperazine (10 g., 0.11M) in toluene (75 ml.) was added dropwise acetic acid with warming of the reaction mixture. The white flocculent precipitate of the piperazine diacetate, which first formed, gradually went into solution. Acetic acid (45 ml., 0.75M) was added in total. Complete separation of water required two and half hours. The dark red liquid was cooled, washed thoroughly with water. The water extract as before yielded piperazine diacetate. The hydrocarbon layer yielded 40 g. (85% of theoretical) of the desired condensation product, b.p. 98°/1.5 mm.

Attempts at the Condensation of Camphor with Ethyl Cyanoacetate: 'Lot addition technique' of Catalyst (Cragoe et al., loc. cit.). Single solvent: Toluene.—A mixture of camphor (5 g., 0.033M), ethyl cyanoacetate (4 g.; 0.033 M), piperazine (0.3 g., 0.003 M), acetic acid (6 ml., 0.1 M) and toluene (75 ml.) was refluxed for one and half hours and a further amount of piperazine (0.2 g., 0.002 M), ethyl cyanoacetate (1.5 g., 0.01 M) and acetic acid (3 ml., 0.05 M) were added and refluxed for one hour. After a further addition of ethyl cyanoacetate (2 g., 0.015 M) and acetic acid (5 ml., 0.08 M) the mixture was refluxed for one hour more. On working up, the camphor was recovered unchanged.

An attempt to condense camphor with ethyl cyanoacetate by applying the portionwise addition technique (Cragoe et al., loc. cit.) of the catalyst in a solvent mixture of benzene, chloroform and xylene also failed to yield any product.

Camphor, however, has been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate by the portionwise addition of ammonium acetate (cf. Cragoe, et al., loc. cit.).

Attempts at the Condensation of Methyl ethyl Ketone with Diethyl Malonate.—Methyl ethyl ketone (7.2 g., 0.1 M) together with diethyl malonate (16 g., 0.1 M), piperazine (1.7 g., 0.2 M), acetic acid (6 ml., 0.1M) in chloroform (60 ml.) was refluxed for 2 hours. The constituents were recovered unchanged.

Diethyl malonate could be condensed with reactive aldehydes in the presence of piperidine acetate (Cope et al., loc. cit.). *cyclo*Hexanone was condensed with malonic ester in the presence of sodium ethoxide with sodium iodide catalyst (Giral and Guzman, *Ciencia*, 1946, 2, 39). *cyclo*Pentanone was condensed with the same reagent in presence of acetic anhydride and aniline-zinc chloride complex (Kon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2727).

Condensation of Diethyl Acetone Dicarboxylate with Ethyl Cyanoacetate.—To diethylacetone dicarboxylate (44 g., 0.21 M), ethyl cyanoacetate (25 g., 0.22 M), acetic acid (10.5 ml., 0.2 M) in toluene (75 ml.) was added piperazine diacetate (prepared from piperazine, 3.7 g. and acetic acid, 5 ml.) and refluxed for one hour. On working up

the yield of the colorless liquid product was 20 g. (30% of theoretical), b.p. $155^{\circ}/6$ mm. (Found: C, 56.44; H, 6.99; N, 4.66. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{18}O_6N$: C, 56.55; H, 6.3; N, 4.71 per cent).

From the aqueous extract the catalyst was recovered.

**Condensation of Mesityl Oxide with Ethyl Cyanoacetate.*—To a refluxing solution of ethyl cyanoacetate (5.65 g.), acetic acid (2.5 ml.) in toluene (70 ml.) containing piperazine diacetate was added dropwise the freshly distilled mesityl oxide (5 g., 0.06 M) during 2½ hours. On working up a colorless, rubber-smelling liquid was obtained, yield 5 g. (55% of theoretical), b.p. $100^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found: C, 67.86; H, 7.60; N, 7.31. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}O_2N$: C, 68.39; H, 7.77; N, 7.25 per cent).

Aqueous extract yielded some of the catalyst.

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* Knoevenagel condensation between an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone and a reactive methylene compound has been described by Knoevenagel (*loc. cit.*).